

Upshot of Percentage Consistency and the Sum-of-Pairs Score Factor on the Algorithmic Structures of some DNA Analysis Tools

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ABSTRACT

One of the most popular quantitative measurements for multiple sequence alignment (MSA) is the Sum-of-Pair score, or simply sum-of-pair (SP). Sum-of-pairs scoring of multiple alignments is a potentially biased scoring measure. If the input sequences are not independent but instead over-sample some groups compared to others, the higher number of pairwise alignments to an over-sampled group can dominate the alignment score. This greater contribution of an over-sampled group to the score will tend to drive the multiple alignments toward improving the pairwise alignments to such groups at the price of worsening the pairwise alignments to under-sampled groups, thus degrading the overall quality of the alignment.

Keywords:

Sum-of-pairs score, Percentage Consistency, Algorithmic approaches, DNA sequencing tools, Jalveiw, Sequencing methods,

1.1 Introduction

Biologist-friendly software tools are crucial in this age of burgeoning sequence databases. These tools not only make it possible to use computational and statistical methods, but also allow scientists to select methods and algorithms best suited to understand the function, structure, evolution, and adaptation of genes and species, (Butler, 2012), . The flood of data acquired from the increasing number of publicly available databases has led to new demands for bio-informatics software. With the growing amount of information resulting from high throughput experiments, new questions arise that often focus on the comparison of genes, genomes, and their expression profiles. Inferring new knowledge by combining different kinds of post-genomics data obviously necessitates the development of new approaches that allow the integration of variable data sources into a flexible framework, (Catherine et al., 2011).

In the context of an explosion of new data management challenges, the field of bio-informatics is rapidly becoming the most critical step in realizing the full potential of genomics and proteomics. Population geneticists, ecologists, epidemiologists, and clinical researchers, have routinely used statistical and computational models to evaluate information they have collected. However, new breeds of life scientists are applying new analytical techniques to new types of data, (Clamp *et al.*, 2004).

Many data mining, annotation, and visualization systems have been developed over the last couple of years, each with their advantages and limitations. Additionally,

several stand-alone tools have been introduced, which rely on object-oriented programming languages, e.g. Strainer: Software for analysis of population variation in community genomic datasets or MetaLook: 3D visualization software for marine ecological genomics. They have been designed to facilitate the exploration and analysis of highly specific datasets. Moreover, they are user-friendly and offer simple installation procedures. A shift from process to object oriented programming languages is a current trend in biologist-centric software development. The rise of bioinformatics to its current prominence has paralleled the growth of the Human Genome Project, thereby paving ways for more DNA sequence software with diversity in content.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The genome sequencing revolution is approaching a landmark figure of 1500 completely sequenced genomes. Coupled with fast-declining, per-base sequencing costs, this influx of DNA sequence data has encouraged laboratory scientists to engage large data sets in comparative sequence analyses for making evolutionary, functional and transitional inferences. Sum-of-pairs scoring of multiple alignments is a potentially biased scoring measure. If the input sequences are not independent but instead over-sample some groups compared to others, the higher number of pairwise alignments to an over-sampled group can dominate the alignment score. This greater contribution of an over-sampled group to the score will tend to drive the multiple alignments toward improving the pairwise alignments to such groups at the price of worsening the pairwise alignments to under-sampled groups, thus degrading the overall quality of the alignment. Again, creating a direct perturbation to the percentage consistency of the entire process. Therefore, there is need to x-ray the effect of sum-of-pairs scoring on the percentage consistency and the alignment result.

1.3 Aim and objectives of the study

This is aim at analyzing the diversity in content and algorithm structure of DNA sequence data software(s), and recommends a more standardized set of modules and algorithm for different quest with respect to accuracy, time of execution and robustness of the system.

To achieve this aim, the following objectives were set for use.

1. To establish the possible upshot of the Percentage consistency and the Sum-of-pair factors on the alignment tools.

1.4 Motivation and Significance of the studying

The application of analytical software in live science, specifically in DNA and protein sequences data analytical has expose users and researches to a dilemma of extensive review of such software in order to ascertain and consider which of the software that is most suitable for the application and why. The reasons for the particular interest in molecular biology are, first, that it is a growing and important area of scientific study, and second, the lengths of biological sequences are such that the need for efficient methods of sequence analysis is becoming acute

2.0 Review of related works

2.1 Genetic analysis software

The Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA)

The Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA) software is a desktop application designed for comparative analysis of homologous gene sequences either from multi-gene families or from different species with a special emphasis on inferring evolutionary relationships and patterns of DNA and protein evolution. In addition to the tools for statistical analysis of data, MEGA provides many convenient facilities for the assembly of sequence data sets from files or web-based repositories, and it includes tools for visual presentation of the results obtained in the form of interactive phylogenetic trees and evolutionary distance matrices, (Davulur and Zhang, 2003).

The MEGA software project grew out of the need for employing statistical methods in the phylogenetic analysis of DNA and protein sequences in the early 1990s. At this time, most computer programs available did not allow us to explore their primary data visually and lacked a user-friendly interface. There were two primary general-purpose computer programs for inferring phylogenetic trees. One was PAUP for constructing parsimony trees, and the other was PHYLIP for inferring phylogenetic trees using various character and statistical methods such as maximum likelihood, parsimony, and distance methods, (Kriventseva, 2001).

GenAIEx (Genetic Analysis in Excel)

GenAIEx was originally developed as a teaching tool to facilitate teaching population genetic analysis at the graduate level (Markowitz et al, 2007). GenAIEx operates within Microsoft Excel and widely used spread sheet software that forms part of the cross platform Microsoft Office suite. Packaging genetic analysis within a familiar and flexible environment resulted in quick understanding and effective performance of population genetic analyses. Taking advantage of the rich graphical options available within Excel, GenAIEx offers a wide range of graphical outputs that aid genetic data analysis and interpretation. GenAIEx is now widely used by university teachers at both undergraduate and graduate levels around the world. Moreover, the software has also attracted a large number of researchers who utilize its unique features.

GenAIEx offers population genetic analysis of diploid dominant, haploid, haplotypic and binary genetic data from animals, plants and microorganisms. It accommodates a wide range of genetic markers, including microsatellites SQL server reporting servers (SSRs), single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), amplified fragment length polymorphisms and DNA sequences. Both allele frequency-based and distance based analysis options are provided. The former includes estimates of heterozygosity and genetic diversity, F-statistics, Nei's genetic distance, population assignment and relatedness. The latter includes Analysis of Molecular Variance (ANOVA), Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA), Mantel tests, TwoGener, multivariate and 2D spatial autocorrelation, (Panchenko and Bryant, 2002).

GenAIEx maintains backward compatibility, but it provides access to the expanded spread sheet of Excel 2007 onward. Thus, the maximum numbers of loci and samples are vastly expanded and only constrained by memory. More than 30 different Excel graphs summarize the outcomes of genetic analyses. Graphics can be further

manipulated with Excel options and easily converted to pdf or other publication quality formats.

2.2 DNA sequencing methods

Dynamic programming method

Dynamic programming is a method that determines optimal alignment by matching two sequences for all possible pairs of characters between the two sequences. It is fundamentally similar to the dot matrix method in that it also creates a two-dimensional alignment grid. However, it finds alignment in a more quantitative way by converting a dot matrix into a scoring matrix to account for matches and mismatches between sequences. By searching for the set of highest scores in this matrix, the best alignment can be accurately obtained.

Dynamic programming works by first constructing a two-dimensional matrix whose axes are the two sequences to be compared. The residue matching is according to a particular scoring matrix. The scores are calculated one row at a time. This starts with the first row of one sequence, which is used to scan through the entire length of the other sequence, followed by scanning of the second row. The matching scores are calculated. The scanning of the second row takes into account the scores already obtained in the first round. The best score is put into the bottom right corner of an intermediate matrix, dynamic programming for local alignment. In regular sequence alignment, the divergence level between the two sequences to be aligned is not easily known. The sequence lengths of the two sequences may also be unequal. In such cases, identification of regional sequence similarity may be of greater significance than finding a match that includes all residues. The first application of dynamic programming in local alignment is the Smith–Waterman algorithm. In this algorithm, positive scores are assigned for matching residues and zeros for mismatches. No negative scores are used. A similar tracing-back procedure is used in dynamic programming. However, the alignment path may begin and end internally along the main diagonal. It starts with the highest scoring position and proceeds diagonally up to the left until reaching a cell with a zero.

Maximum Likelihood (ML)

Another character-based approach is ML, which uses probabilistic models to choose a best tree that has the highest probability or likelihood of reproducing the observed data. It finds a tree that most likely reflects the actual evolutionary process. ML is an exhaustive method that searches every possible tree topology and considers every position in an alignment, not just informative sites. (Ogban et al 2019) By employing a particular substitution model that has probability values of residue substitutions, ML calculates the total likelihood of ancestral sequences evolving to internal nodes and eventually to existing sequences. It sometimes also incorporates parameters that account for rate variations across sites.

ML works by calculating the probability of a given evolutionary path for a particular extant sequence. The probability values are determined by a substitution model (either for nucleotides or amino acids), (Thompson, 2006).

For other substitution models, the formulas are much more complex and are not described here. For a particular site, the probability of a tree path is the product of the probability from the root to all the tips, including every intermediate branch in the tree topology. Because multiplication often results in very small values, it is

computationally more convenient to express all probability values as natural log likelihood values, which also converts multiplication into summation.

Neighbor-joining (NJ)

The Unweight Pair Group Method (UPGMA) method uses unweight distances and assume that all taxa have constant evolutionary rates. Since this molecular clock assumption is often not met in biological sequences, to build a more accurate phylogenetic trees, the neighbor joining (NJ) method can be used, which is somewhat similar to UPGMA in that it builds a tree by using stepwise reduced distance matrices. However, the NJ method does not assume the taxa to be equidistant from the root. It corrects for unequal evolutionary rates between sequences by using a conversion step, (Waterhouse *et al.*, 2009).

Maximum parsimony

The parsimony method chooses a tree that has the fewest evolutionary changes or shortest overall branch lengths. It is based on a principle related to a medieval philosophy called Occam's razor. The theory was formulated by William of Occam in the thirteenth century and states that the simplest explanation is probably the correct one. This is because the simplest explanation requires the fewest assumptions and the fewest leaps of logic. In dealing with problems that may have an infinite number of possible solutions, choosing the simplest model may help to "shave off" those variables that are not really necessary to explain the phenomenon. By doing this, model development may become easier, and there may be less chance of introducing inconsistencies, ambiguities, and redundancies, hence, the name Occam's razor. For phylogenetic analysis, parsimony seems a good assumption. By this principle, a tree with the least number of substitutions is probably the best to explain the differences among the taxa under study. This view is justified by the fact that evolutionary changes are relatively rare within a reasonably short time frame. This implies that a tree with minimal changes is likely to be a good estimate of the true tree. By minimizing the changes, the method minimizes the phylogenetic noise owing to homoplasy and independent evolution, (Zhang *et al.*, 2002).

3.1 Methodology

The DNA sequence analysis application reference was built using the agile software development method. The agile software development methodology is focused around a short iterative software release cycle. This design is geared toward heavily involving the stakeholders and constantly showing them demonstrations of the current state of the software. This allows for the stakeholders to make recommendations and suggest changes while the software is being actively developed so that the software can track what the customers actually desire. Agile also helps software projects improve the expectations of when software will be completed, determine what items can feasibly go into a release cycle, and provide the ability to easily track overall project progress.

Netbeans Integrated Development Environment (IDE) was used for the implementation of the software. Netbeans IDE (version is 3.6) is an open source Java development tool (current Java version is 1.4.2). The System Analysis and Alignment (SAAS) application was designed and developed to run on all windows operating system. Since the application (which includes graphical display and sequence analysis algorithms implementation) is written using Java programming language (version

1.4.2), it can be run on any computer platforms which has a Java Virtual Machine (JVM) installed.

The system architecture of the application has a link to the GeneBank database to get all the possible DNA sample data; figure 1. Again, a set of DNA sequence analysis algorithms, and a Java GUI based DNA analysis tool for results display and sequences manipulation facilities.

Figure 1: SAAS Architecture

However, due to the confidentiality and sensitivity nature of the data (i.e. involving human DNA), a high security clearance from the relevant authorities is required in order to have access to the real data, which makes it difficult to acquire real data for the system. Therefore, in this work test data, a combination of self-generation data supplemented by data obtained from the Internet Genome Databases will be used.

Materials and methods

Materials

Eleven (11) multiple sequence alignment tools were installed on a HP EliteBook Folio9470m computer running with windows 10 operating system and each program was tested using default parameters. The choice of the 11 multiple sequence alignment tools were dependent on the sequence to be aligned. In the research work, a comparative study of the 11 most used MSA tools based on it algorithmic approach, namely: ClustalW, MEGA , T-Coffee, Muscle, Mafft, ProbCons, Kalign, MSAProbs, GLProbs, Clustal Omega and MSProbs was done.

Methods

First, sequences with different class labels will be combined to generate each benchmark dataset. Then, the alignment analyses will be performed using 11 multiple sequence alignment (MSA) and 1(one) Pair-wise Sequence Alignment (PSA) methods

and the aligned sequence matrices with gaps inserted will be generated as outputs. Based on this, evaluation calculation was performed by cluster validity calculation using Sum-of Pairs (SW) and Silhouette Width (RS scores), based on distances calculation results. Significance analyses will be performed on biological and statistical levels to determine whether the performance differences between algorithms produces essential discriminations on application scope and then after result will be discussion. Finally application development will follow.

Online Data Linking

We choose the globin genes of 11 species, which are widely used for evaluating the performance of sequence similarity analysis methods. This data was obtained from genebank (Table 1).

For each dataset, we combined DNA sequences of different protein families into one file. All the protein families and sequences were included in the analyses except for the sequences that belonged to more than one protein families since they would cause the confusion of the following steps. Each protein sequence was considered as a sample and the family it belonged to was considered as the sample's class label. The original family labels of the sequences are considered as the ground truth of the clustering results.

Table 1: Globin genes of 11 species *Source: Genebank*

S/N	SPECIES	ACCESSION NUMBER	LOCATION	LENGTH(nt)
1	Bovine	[GenBank:X00376]	278-1741	1464
2	Chimpanzee	[GenBank:X02345]	4189-5532	1344
3	Gallus	[GenBank:V00409]	465-1810	1346
4	Goat	[GenBank:M15387]	279-1749	1471
5	Gorilla	[GenBank:X61109]	4538-5881	1344
6	Human	[GenBank:U01317]	62187-63610	1424
7	Lemur	[GenBank:M15734]	154-1595	1442
8	Mouse	[GenBank:V00722]	275-1462	1188
9	Opossum	[GenBank:J03643]	467-2488	2022
10	Rabbit	[GenBank:V00882]	277-1419	1143
11	Rat	[GenBank:X06701]	310-1505	1196

MSA methods evaluated and Benchmarks

To evaluate different alignment tools effectively, there is need to have some benchmark sequences and “gold standard” reference alignments of those sequences. For assessing the performance of different automated alignment tools, it is required to find a quantitative accuracy relative to gold standard reference alignments. Popular benchmark databases of hand-curated reference alignments include BALiBASE and HOMSTRAD. A number of modern alignment databases rely on automated structural alignment protocols, including SABmark PREFAB, OxBench , and BALiBASE version 3. Among them, the most widely applied database is BALiBASE that contains a C-language application, called bali-score, which measure the *SP* (Sum of Pairs) and the *TC* (Total Column) score of test alignment in comparison to the reference alignment will be used in this research work

The 11 MSA tools were selected based on two parameters: (1) the underlying algorithms and (2) their popularity. Table 2 describes the MSA tools with their versions, main algorithms, and URL for download. All these MSA methods were run using default parameters.

TABLE 2: Multiple sequence alignment program use comparatively in this research

S/N	MSA METHOD	VERSION	MAIN ALGORITHM	AVAILABILITY
1	T-Coffee	3.27	Consistency (multi-core usage capable)	http://www.tcoffee.org/
2	ProbCons	1.1	Consistency	http://probcons.stanford.edu/download.html
3	Kalign	1.04	Progressive (Wu-Manber)	http://msa.sbc.su.se/cgi-bin/msa.cgi
4	MEGA 7.0	7.0	Consistency	
5	GLprobs	1.2	Progressive	https://sourceforge.net/projects/glprobs/files/latest/download
6	MSAprobs	1.4	Progressive	http://MSAprobs.cbrc.jp/alignment/software/
7	Clustal W	1.8	Hidden Markov Model	http://www.clustal.org/omega/
8	MUSCLE	3.6	Iterative	http://www.drive5.com/MUSCLE/downloads.htm
9	MAFFT	5.732	Iterative	http://mafft.cbrc.jp/alignment/software/
10	Clustal Omega	1.2.2	Progressive	Source code .tar.gz (1.2.4)
11	MSprobs	2.4	Progressive	http://MSprobs.cbrc.jp/alignment/software/

4.0 System Implementation and Results

The programming language use in implementing a system is typically chosen based on the features offered by the language that makes it suitable to solve the problem at hand. The important factor to consider during the chosen of a programming language include the target operating environment in which the system will be deployed and used and the ease of maintaining the system development afforded by the language. The implementation of this tool was done using the PHP ((hypertext processor) programming language.

TABLE 3: MSA Result Comparison Analysis Table.

S/N	MSA TOOLS	% consistency	sum of pairs scores	column scores(no gaps)	column scores(with gaps)	min #seq for cs
1	T-Coffee	64.55	0.9	0.567	0.567	6
2	ProbCons	46.55	0.912	0.423	0.423	6
3	Kalign	45.55	0.917	0.422	0.422	6
4	MEGA 7.0	45.55	0.942	0.573	0.573	6
5	GLprobs	56.706	0.938	0.562	0.554	6
6	MSAprobs	56.706	0.934	0.565	0.545	6
7	Clustal W	43.805	0.915	0.409	0.409	6
8	MUSCLE	45.675	0.916	0.42	0.419	6
9	MAFFT	44.118	0.914	0.407	0.406	6
10	ClustalOmega	43.63	0.915	0.409	0.409	6
11	MSprobs	56.706	0.934	0.565	0.545	6

Sum of pair's scores

One of the most popular quantitative measurement for multiple sequence alignment (MSA) is the Sum-of-Pair score, or simply sum-of-pair (SP), figure 2. Sum-of-pairs scoring of multiple alignments is a potentially biased scoring measure. If the input sequences are not independent but instead over-sample some groups compared to others, the higher number of pairwise alignments to an over-sampled group can dominate the alignment score.

Figure 2: Chart showing the enlarged Percentage Consistency compared to the other factors.

This greater contribution of an over-sampled group to the score will tend to drive the multiple alignments toward improving the pairwise alignments to such groups at the price of worsening the pairwise alignments to under-sampled groups, Figure 3 thus degrading the overall quality of the alignment. Mega and Clustal W outperform other multiple sequence alignment tools.

FIG. 3: Bar Chart showing the sum of pair scores compare to other multiple sequence alignment tools.

5.1 Summary

Choosing the most suitable program to a dataset alignment is difficult. SAAS will help young and inexperienced bioinformatics to choose the right tools for sequence alignment analysis. However, with regards to the available tools, Mega outperformed others in the control and use of Sum-of-Pairs scoring.

5.2 Conclusion

Running MSA programs with default parameters are usually preferred when no information regarding the sequences to be aligned are available and/or for users without previous knowledge in this particular field of sequence analysis. With that in mind, we chose to benchmark a selection of programs mostly with their default options. Although results presented herein are compatible with current low-cost hardware and timelines of most research projects, they must be used only as guidelines, and we encourage users to carefully study each program's parameters in order to obtain the best possible output. The BALiBASE suite is a reliable benchmarking dataset, but still might be considered small to meet certain MSA projects. Thus, understanding each program's own limitations are imperative in order to generate reliable results.

5.3 Recommendation

It is clear that future work to improve alignment programs should concentrate on the problems of large insertions, extensions and sequence fragments. The alignment of sequences of similar length is relatively successful, even if there is only weak identity between the sequences. Another important area of interest which is becoming more and more frequent is the alignment of families of sequences. Increasing the number of sequences in an alignment set often significantly improves the alignment quality of divergent sequences.

The results of this program comparison may be used to indicate the most suitable program for a particular alignment problem. It should now be possible to predetermine the nature of a set of sequences, in particular the re-partition of sequence identities and the presence of unequal length sequences. An alignment server would then be able to automatically select the program which is likely to give the most accurate results.

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